

SOCIO-LEGAL LIABILITY OF ONLINE GAMBLING AND BETTING IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15461203>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10- May 2025 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15-May 2025 yil
Nashr qilindi: 19-May 2025 yil

KEY WORDS

online gambling, ludomania, digital technologies, legal regulation, Uzbekistan, social security.

ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the social, psychological, and legal impacts of online gambling, which has become widespread in recent years due to the development of digital technologies, on society and individuals. The formation of the legislative framework in Uzbekistan, issues of control and legal regulation of online gambling will also be considered. The article examines methods of combating online gambling based on national and international best practices.

In recent years, with the development of digital technologies, online gambling has become an integral part of people's lives. As a result of factors such as social inequality, unemployment, and psychological vulnerability in society, certain segments of the population are increasingly being drawn into such games. Gambling, especially when carried out through internet platforms, is often left outside legal control. The UN's 2022 report noted that online gambling is exacerbating mental health problems on a global scale [1]. According to statistics, the number of people worldwide suffering from gambling addiction - ludomania - exceeded 15 million in 2023, and this figure continues to grow every year [2].

This affliction, widespread among the general population, negatively impacts not only the individual's financial situation but also their mental well-being. As psychologist A.V. Lebedev noted, "gambling urge is a psychological state that consciously binds a person to a certain activity, and over time, it limits individual freedom" [3, 56]. As a result of such games, there are many cases of falling under not only a financial influence, but also an emotional influence that leads to addiction. Furthermore, another negative consequence of online gambling is the emergence of serious problems not only at the personal level but also at the family, economic, and legal levels.

The attitude towards gambling has existed in various societies since ancient times. For example, in Islamic sources, this activity is strictly forbidden. In the Quran, in Surah Al-Ma'idah (verses 90-91), it is stated: "... gambling, drinking, idols, and fortune-telling - these are the works of Satan, stay away from them" [4].

Gambling was first criminalized in Uzbekistan under the USSR Criminal Code on August 11, 1988, by order of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the RSFSR. This act was classified as a crime and included in Chapter X of the Criminal Code of that time. Chapter X is

titled "Crimes Against Public Safety, Public Order, and Public Health" [5]. Previously, only administrative liability for gambling was applied. However, even after criminalization, criminal liability was imposed only after repeated commission of the same crime within one year of being subjected to administrative liability. In Uzbekistan, gambling was officially banned from September 22, 1994, based on Article 278 of the Criminal Code.

Today, this problem remains a relevant and complex issue. In particular, there are serious problems in identifying gambling activities occurring through online programs, establishing their legal liability, and eliminating these violations in practice.

It is suggested that this crime be analyzed not only in the traditional sense, but also within the framework of cybercrime. For example, mobile applications of foreign platforms such as "1xBet" and "Parimatch" are accessible to users in Uzbekistan without any permission [6].

Positive changes have been observed in legislation in recent years. For example, since 2021, the government of Uzbekistan has developed a digital security strategy and is introducing a mechanism for applying technical blocks to illegal gambling content on the internet. This means combating modern crime through modern solutions. The ongoing blocking of illegal gambling and betting sites by the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications in 2023 is one of the positive measures to prevent this problem. At the same time, it is recommended that mechanisms related to psychological support and social rehabilitation should also be included in such measures.

Moreover, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, offenses related to gambling are regulated by Article 278 of the Criminal Code. This article defines the organization and conduct of gambling and other games based on risk as a crime. This provision is established not only as a punitive measure, but also as a legal instrument aimed at ensuring public health. Furthermore, amendments to the Criminal Code introduce administrative warnings followed by criminal liability for those who promote gambling. This ensures a balance between prevention and punishment.

At present, gambling is often practiced through phone apps. This situation complicates the search for the responsible person. Firstly, the phone app belongs to a legal entity, and the functionality of these games is programmed. According to our national legislation, only individuals are held liable. Secondly, most of these phone apps are located abroad. For example, the headquarters of the "1xbet" company is located in Limassol, Cyprus. The company "BWIN" is located in Vienna, Republic of Austria, and the company "Parimatch" is located in Ukraine. It has its own headquarters in Kyiv. The resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan on several related issues is considered necessary.

Therefore, when classifying gambling as a crime, not only material damage but also moral and social harm must be taken into account. Although ludomania has not yet been recognized as a separate disease in Uzbekistan, specialized centers should be established in this area within the healthcare system.

Currently, gambling has become widespread not only in its traditional form but also via digital platforms, has become one of the factors threatening social stability. This is reflected in Article 278 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which classifies this activity as a crime, recognizing it as a dangerous process that undermines a person's social status and

weakens their spiritual and financial freedom.

An effective fight against gambling should be based not only on punishment but also on the development of public awareness and culture. The promotion of a healthy lifestyle through social advertising, cinema, theater, and blogging platforms has yielded positive results.

Gambling addiction is often a manifestation of underlying psychological issues. To prevent this, psychological counseling centers have been established in several regions of Uzbekistan. For example, gambling are provided through Psychological Assistance and Rehabilitation Centers operating in regions such as Tashkent, Samarkand, and Fergana.

The government is promoting employment and a purposeful lifestyle for young people through programs such as the "Youth Notebook" and "Dialogue with Youth." In our view, these measures contribute directly to building public resilience against addiction and related disorders.

Furthermore, ensuring digital security, restricting access to illegal foreign platforms, and enhancing mechanisms for their detection and comprehensive regulation are current imperatives. In this effort, alongside the state, the participation of civil society institutions, the media, and citizens is crucial.

In international practice, for example, in Germany, gambling is strictly controlled on the basis of a state license [7]. In the US, although gambling is legal in some states, there are strict penalties at the federal level for its promotion or illegal organization [8]. In Great Britain, the Gambling Commission operates as a special regulatory body [9].

Gambling is legal in Great Britain but is strictly regulated by the Gambling Commission. There is even a restriction for game participants; in some cases, they must obtain membership cards issued by the relevant authority, which may be valid for a limited period, such as 24 hours [10].

In Switzerland, considered one of the world's safest banks and a leader in average salary ratings, gambling is regulated by constitutional law. According to Article 106 of the new Constitution adopted in 1999, legislation on gambling and lotteries is regulated by federal law, with consideration of European standards. The establishment of gambling establishments and the hiring of employees are carried out by licensed individuals or entities authorized by the competent gambling authority [11]. Furthermore, this constitutional article requires that licensing authorities consider the specific regional characteristics and risks associated with gambling to consider the specifics of the territory and the inherent risks of gambling when issuing licenses [12].

In conclusion, it can be said that online gambling is a pressing socio-legal problem for society today. They negatively affect not only a person's financial situation, but also their psychological and social well-being. The development of the legislative framework related to gambling in Uzbekistan and the implementation of digital security strategies are key directions for effectively addressing this problem. Along with legal measures, psychological support and outreach and education initiatives play a significant role in combating the problem of gambling. It is also necessary to limit the spread of gambling by drawing on international experience and monitoring digital platforms.

References:

1. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti. (2022). World Drug Report 2022.

- <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/data-and-analysis/world-drug-report-2022.html>
2. Karimova Z.M. "Raqamli xavfsizlik va jinoyatlarning yangi shakllari", Yuridik fanlar jurnal, 2023, №4.1. World Health Organization. (2023). Gambling and gaming addiction: Public health implications. Geneva: WHO Press. ISBN 978-92-4-007304-6.
 3. Лебедев, А.В. (2018). Психология азартного поведения. Москва: Питер. — Б. 56.
 4. The Holy Qur'an. (2004). Surah Al-Ma'idah, Verses 90–91. Translation by M.A.S. Abdel Haleem. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
 5. Prezidium of the Supreme Soviet of the RSFSR. (1988). Decree No. 9326-XI on Criminalization of Gambling. Moscow.
 6. O'zbekistonda onlayn qimor o'yinlari taqiqlandi. 2023. URL: <https://qalampir.uz/news/uzbekistonda-onlayn-qimor-oyinlari-taqiqlandi-94112>
 7. Bundesministerium der Justiz. Glücksspielstaatsvertrag (GlüStV). 2021. URL: <https://www.idnow.io/blog/online-gambling-germany-regulations/>
 8. Casetext. 18 U.S. Code § 1084 - Transmission of wagering information. URL: <https://casetext.com/statute/united-states-code/title-18-crimes-and-criminal-procedure/part-i-crimes/chapter-50-gambling/section-1084>
 9. UK Gambling Commission. About us. URL: <https://www.gamblingcommission.gov.uk/about-us/who-we-are>
 10. United Kingdom Parliament. Gambling Act 2005. URL: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2005/19/contents>
 11. Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft. Federal Constitution of the Swiss Confederation, Article 106. URL: <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/1999/404/en>
 12. Swiss Federal Gaming Board (SFGB). Regulation of Casinos. URL: <https://www.esbk.admin.ch/esbk/en/home.html>

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